

EUROqCHARM

EUROpean quality Controlled Harmonization Assuring Reproducible Monitoring and
assessment of plastic pollution

Tools for assessing the methods and protocols used in the analysis of nano-, micro-, and macroplastic

EUROqCHARM Short Report

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About EUROqCHARM

This report is part of a project that has received funding from European Union's Horizon 2020 Coordination and Support Action programme under Grant Agreement 101003805 (EUROqCHARM).

Plastic pollution has become a global environmental and societal concern in recent years. Numerous protocols have been developed to monitor plastic litter globally, but these are rarely comparable. This has hindered gathering of knowledge regarding pollution sources, development of monitoring programmes and risk assessments, and implementation of mitigation measures. To develop long-term solutions to reduce plastic pollution, it is essential to establish harmonised methodologies. EUROqCHARM will address this by critically reviewing state-of-the-art analytical methods and, taking harmonisation one step further, validating them through an interlaboratory comparison (ILC) study. This will bring together prominent laboratories in environmental plastics analysis and will produce certified reference materials to be marketed for at least three of the four target matrices (water, soil/sediment, biota, air), during and after project completion.

EUROqCHARM recognises that harmonisation for large scale monitoring requires flexibility, comparability and reliability. We will identify Reproducible Analytical Pipelines (RAP), resulting in a catalogue of RAP procedures for nano-, micro- and macro-plastics for the four target matrices. Each RAP will be validated in terms of Technology Readiness Level (TRL) to decide if further validation is needed (by ILC).

Blueprints for standards, recommendations for policy and legislation and support for the establishment of acceptable reference levels and environmental targets will be given. This will include a roadmap for harmonised data collection and management, where policy analysis and coherence will be integral parts. To maximise impact, EUROqCHARM will also establish and consolidate an operational network for plastic monitoring, stimulating Transnational Joint Actions built on existing and future European and international initiatives.

The multi-stakeholder composition of EUROqCHARM puts the group in a unique position to achieve these ambitious goals.

More information on the project can be found at: www.EUROqCHARM.eu

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Executive Summary

In WP1 of the EUROqCHARM project, a Systematic Review (SR) was carried out to analyse the matrix- and size- adapted methods currently used for plastic pollution research and monitoring. This report presents the main concepts and methodology used to identify the properties of fundamental steps in the analytical process and the methods and protocols that are more widely used for monitoring available in the scientific literature.

Methodological steps from sampling to data management were arranged in Reproducible Analytical Pipelines (RAPs) and assessed for the Technological Readiness Level (TRL), which may eventually (if not already) be incorporated into plastic monitoring programmes.

Optimising the processes involved in plastic monitoring and analysis is of high priority. Therefore, by introducing RAPs into plastics pollution research, EUROqCHARM has been providing guidance for the coordination of monitoring activities at the European level, whilst strengthening the generation of sound scientific knowledge to support strategic actions. The goal of WP1 was achieved through four tasks addressing plastics in different matrices (water, soil/sediment, air, biota) and in different size ranges (nano, micro, macroplastics). Thus, this report is accompanied by four additional reports focusing on the results for the individual matrices.

Robust and repeatable methods were regularly used in some papers. These were also reflective of complete and mature RAPs that have either already been included in monitoring guidelines or, have the properties of a high TRL to be recommended for monitoring. In other instances, technology was available but not yet mature to be rolled out as a tool for monitoring, or, as in the case of air, still at the pioneering stage of science.

This report is not intended to define the best methods and protocols for analysis, which is the objective of other work packages in EUROqCHARM and dedicated Working Groups, but aims to identify the properties of the fundamental steps of the analytical process and the methods and protocols that are more widely used for monitoring as from scientific literature.

We **showcase the potential of integration of TRLs and RAPs as a tool for systematic description** of analytical procedures for plastics in the environment and as a fundamental decision-making support tool. To support monitoring, it is necessary to define recommended approaches, which are reproducible and comparable when applied between national, regional, and local scales. Such methods cannot be recommended if they do not meet the requirements of a certain TRL level.

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- Task 1.2 - Sebastian Primpke, Lise Rocher (AWI), Amy Lusher (NIVA), Stefano Aliani, Giuseppe Suaria, Andrea Paluselli (CNR-ISMAR).
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List of acronyms

Acronyms	Definition
AMAP	Arctic Monitoring and Assessment Programme
EU	European Union
GESAMP	Group of Experts on the Scientific Aspects of Marine Environmental Protection
HELCOM	Baltic Marine Environment Protection Commission
ILC	Interlaboratory Comparison exercise
ISO	International Organisation for Standards
JAMSTEC	Japan Agency for Marine-Earth Science and Technology
MSFD	Marine Strategy Framework Directive
NOAA	National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration
OSPAR	Oslo-Paris Convention
RAPs	Reproducible Analytical Pipelines
SR	Systematic Review
SWOT	Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, Threats
TGML	Technical Group on Marine Litter
TRL	Technological Readiness Level
UN	United Nations
UNEP	United Nations Environment Programme
WP	Work Package

Acronym	Full name
NIVA	Norsk institutt for vannforskning <i>Norwegian Institute for Water Research</i>
CNR-ISMAR	Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche – Istituto di Scienze Marine <i>National Research Council, Institute of Marine Sciences (Italy)</i>
SALT	
CSIC	Agencia Estatal Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Cientificas <i>Spanish Research Council</i>
NILU	Norsk institutt for luftforskning <i>Norwegian Institute for Air Research</i>
ILVO	Instituut voor Landbouw- en Visserijonderzoek <i>Flemish Institute for Agricultural and Fisheries Research</i>
AWI	Alfred-Wegener-Institut Helmholtz- Zentrum für Polar- und Meeresforschung <i>Alfred Wegener Institute for Polar and Marine Research</i>
AU	Aarhus University
EAWAG	Eidgenössische Anstalt für Wasserversorgung, Abwasserreinigung und Gewässerschutz <i>Swiss Federal Institute of Aquatic Science and Technology</i>

1. Premise – background of EUROqCHARM WP1

1.1. Objectives

WP1. Screening and analysis of existing methods and protocols for plastic pollution monitoring

The goal of the EUROqCHARM Work Package 1 (WP1) was to **define matrix- and size- adapted methods** which may eventually be incorporated into plastic monitoring programmes. WP1 **used a systematic approach** to assess methods employed by the international research community and identify state-of-the art procedures for sample collection, sample preparation and analysis of plastics from environmental samples **to define matrix- and size- adapted method**.

Reproducible Analytical Pipelines (RAPs) could be extracted for each element in the analytical chain, resulting in a catalogue of RAP procedures. Each RAP assessed in terms of **Technological Readiness Level (TRL)** to decide if further validation is needed.

The workload was thereby **divided across four tasks** addressing plastics in different size ranges (nano-, micro-, macroplastics) in different matrices (water, soil/sediment, air, biota). The specific objectives of WP1 were to:

- Identify existing methods - including the level of currently applied QA/QC procedures for the quantification of nano-, micro-, and macro-plastics in different matrices.
- Evaluate the identified methods for their suitability to be incorporated into monitoring programmes including their advantages and limitations. The most promising methods were suggested for validation and quality control in WP2 or direct implementation into WP3.

Therefore, the **key outputs** of WP1 were to compile existing methods and protocols used to quantify plastics in environmental matrices (using RAPs), evaluate them for further validation (WP2) or direct implementation in monitoring programmes (WP3);

The main actions in WP1 were:

- Systematic literature review;
- Synthesis of existing methods and procedures;
- Compilation of Reproducible Analytical Pipelines (RAPs);
- Analyses of methods Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats (SWOT);
- Suggestions for critical revisions of identified monitoring programmes.

All these actions were attempted for plastic of sizes ranging from macro- to nanoplastics in water, sediment, biota and air, with both marine and terrestrial environments.

In the present report, **the tools developed and applied in the EUROqCHARM project for assessing methods and protocols used in plastics research and monitoring are shortly presented.**

2. Introduction to key concepts

In the early days of plastic pollution research, a standard protocol to measure plastics in the environment did not exist and scientists necessarily applied methods they were familiar with which - following their expertise and skills - they believed to be suitable for collecting reasonable data. Thus, the **number of methods for plastic quantification dramatically increased**.

To provide some order to this scattered approach, organisations including the EU, NOAA, UNEP and JAMSTEC among others, proposed guidelines for sampling and analysis within monitoring programmes (largely focused on shorelines), and many expert groups (e.g., AMAP, GESAMP, OSPAR, TGML, HELCOM etc.) are still working actively on the topic.

This is especially important given that the Global Plastics Treaty is creating a mandate whereby reporting of baselines and progress towards meeting reduction targets is included. Harmonisation of method thus becomes mandatory.

The EUROqCHARM project uses the following **definition for harmonisation**:

***Harmonisation:** the development of a cluster of monitoring procedures – including sampling strategy, sample collection, sample preparation, analysis, quality assurance and quality control criteria, data management protocols – that provide cross-comparable data which can be validated.*

In WP1, a **Systematic Review (SR)** was carried out to analyse the matrix- and size- adapted methods reported in the literature. Methodological steps from sampling to data management were arranged in **Reproducible Analytical Pipelines (RAPs)** and assessed for the **Technological Readiness Level (TRL)**. An outline of the workplan is presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1 – Core concepts of EUROqCHARM WP1 in the context of the subsequent WPs. WP1 focuses on the assessment of existing protocols and methods.

2.1. Plastic pollution terminology

EUROqCHARM appreciates that terminology surrounding plastic pollution is used interchangeably, in different contexts, and by different sectors around the world. It is expected with the recognition of the global agreement on plastics that these definitions will be harmonised globally in the coming years. To reflect the European focus of the project, the following definitions are used:

Plastic: *“Materials consisting of a polymer to which additives or other substances may have been added, and which can function as a main structural component of final products, with the exception of natural polymers that have not been chemically modified. The EU Directive on Single Use Plastics exempts paints, inks and adhesives. The Guidelines further clarify especially the terms ‘natural polymer’ and ‘chemical modification’ to ensure a consistent implementation across the EU” (DIRECTIVE (EU) 2019/904).*

According to **ISO 472:2013**: plastic is a *“material which contains as an essential ingredient a high molecular weight polymer and which, at some stage in its processing into finished products, can be shaped by flow”.*

A synthetic polymer with thermo-plastic or thermo-set properties (synthesized from hydrocarbon or biomass raw materials) and elastomers (e.g., butyl rubber). Many plastics are produced as a mixture of different polymers and various plasticizers, colourants, stabilisers and other additives. Product types can include material fibres, monofilament lines, coatings and ropes (GESAMP 2019).

*** Inconsistencies between these definitions: (1) EU Directive excludes coatings/paints definition; (2) ISO 472:2013 excludes some elastomers (e.g., rubbers). For further discussion of definitions readers are referred to Hartmann et al. (2019).

Litter: *Any persistent, manufactured or processed solid material discarded, disposed of, or abandoned in the (marine and coastal) environment (UNEP 1995).*

The Joint List of Litter Categories for Marine Macrolitter includes the following materials: Cloth/textile, glass/ceramic, metal, artificial polymer materials, paper/cardboard, rubber, processed/worked wood (Fleet et al. 2021).

*** **“Litter”** is the European terminology for solid materials of anthropogenic origin, whereas **“Debris”** is used in primarily in North America.

The size classes of plastic items conform to the general definitions provided by **ISO (ISO/TR 21960:2020)**, whereby:

- Macroplastic:** Fragments and plastic items > 25 mm
- Mesoplastic:** Fragments and Items in the range of 5-25 mm
- Microplastic:** Fragments and Items in the range of 5 mm – 1 µm
- Nanoplastic:** Fragments and Items in the range of 1 µm – 1 nm

*** Many technical reports and guidelines have introduced subcategories for size, usually to accommodate operational (sampling) or analytical (detection) limits. For example, the most recent Arctic Monitoring and Assessment Programme (AMAP) guidelines use the size categories of >1 mm, 1 mm-0.3 mm, 0.3 -0.1 mm and <0.1 mm for water sampling; 5-1 mm, 1 mm- 0.3 mm, <0.3 mm for sediment and soil sampling (AMAP 2021).

2.2. Systematic Review

A **systematic review** (SR) is a research summary that uses a structured, reproducible approach, often supplemented by a meta-analysis to produce an *evidence synthesis* report. EUROqCHARM conducted a SR to sort the available literature for methods used to isolate and identify all sizes of plastics in all environmental matrices, focusing on the methodology.

2.3. Reproducible Analytical Pipelines (RAPs)

Reproducible Analytical Pipelines, or RAPs, are a core component of the EUROqCHARM project. **RAPs refer to the elements which make up an analytical process.** In terms of plastic pollution monitoring, these include the fundamental steps needed for analysis from sample collection to data reporting. RAPs can be built on the principles of reproducibility, replicability and repeatability.

Reproducible analysis is about **breaking down the process of plastic analysis into manageable steps** so that the scientific community can follow the process and understand how results were achieved. In a reproducible workflow, all the fundamental steps used to generate results are identified. This is not intended to force a rigid scheme. But being fully open about the decisions to generate outputs, a RAP aims to make **analysis workflow reproducible and easier for others to quality assure**, assess, and critique. It is a transparent approach which promotes trust because all steps are tracked from start to finish, and helps to support policy with trustworthy and transparent decisions.

The analysis of plastic samples is arranged in recurrent fundamental steps which are addressed to obtain reliable results and can represent the workflow of plastic analysis. Some parts of the workflow have already been identified (e.g., Primpke et al. 2017) but the complete analytical pipeline is yet to be addressed.

There is **no standard procedure to define RAPs in plastic analysis**, given that this a completely new approach. The approach taken by the EUROqCHARM project was to **identify the repeatable fundamental steps for analysis in every environmental matrix** based upon opinion and critical discussion among experts and use the bulk steps to organise the information collected in the SR. The fundamental steps in plastic analysis have been defined (Figure 2) as:

Survey design: This defines the purpose of the survey, including whether there was repeated sampling (monitoring) or single points in time (research), and whether studies used a standardised protocol (e.g., OSPAR) or a method of their own design.

Sample collection: The defines the methods used to collect samples from different matrices in the environment and sub-compartments, also including location, equipment and tools, sample size (e.g., volume), number of replicates and size of target plastics (or litter).

Sample preparation: The process by which target particles are extracted and isolated from the environmental sample. This involved single or multiple steps which are different according to size classes and sample type. For example, sieving, chemical digestion and density separation to remove organic and inorganic, non- target particles.

Analytical detection: This defines the approaches or tools used in the detection of target plastic particles after sample preparation. It includes the use of instruments (e.g., imaging technologies), or the naked eye to detect plastics, as well as the description of the substrate for analysis (e.g., filter papers). This also includes the upper and lower detection limits.

Plastic quantification: This defines the process by which particles are described and confirmed as plastics, as well as quantified. This includes descriptions of particle characteristics (size, shape, colour, polymer), units and metrics used for reporting, procedural blanks and controls.

Data reporting: This defines how data is handled once it is produced, this includes data reporting protocols, treatment, storage and data availability.

Figure 2 – Steps of a Reproducible Analytical Pipeline (RAP) for environmental plastic studies. Orange boxes represent the fundamental steps in plastic analysis. Blue boxes provide an example of elements which form part of the fundamental steps. White boxes represent examples of subRAPs.

RAPs can be interpreted in a bulk approach from survey design to data reporting, if the aim is to study the complete set of methods that fulfil specific needs. For instance, the RAP for seawater is different from sediments and therefore different RAPs will be presented. Each step is a building block in the analytical approach to plastics analysis, so we called them subRAPs (sRAP). The sRAPs can be used to explore the strengths and limitations of a certain step within the pipeline if the objective is to optimize that specific part of a procedure.

Reproducible analysis supports the requirements of a Code of Practice to foster quality assurance and transparency, which results in a series of protocols to analyse plastics in environmental matrices.

2.4. Technological Readiness

The level of maturity of a certain technology is a fundamental aspect in innovation, especially when this technology is critical for the success of a program. When a certain innovation is developed, complete, and ready to use, we consider it mature. The more mature the technology, the lower the risk associated with it, and the more accessible it is for use in everyday applications.

2.4.1. Technological readiness levels (TRLs)

Technological Readiness Levels (TRLs) are a systematic measurement system used to assess the maturity of a particular technology in terms of certain characteristics, as measured by successful tests. It is a guide to structure discussions about the state of development (or maturity) of a single technology and to uncover technical gaps and questions that point toward next steps in the technology’s development. It also helps to identify remaining steps and approximate the level and effort needed to move a technology from its current state into deployment.

TRLs are based on a scale from 1 to 9 with 9 being the most mature technology (Figure 3). The European Commission adopted the TRL approach (Commission Decision C(2014)4995, part 19) and

the TRL scale became, through various modifications, an innovation policy tool of the European Union (EU) (Héder 2017).

Figure 3 – Overview of the nine Technological Readiness Levels (TRLs). TRLs 1-3 represent fundamental R&D (basic research), TRLs 4-5 include scaling and integration (applied research), and TRLs 6-9 include demonstration and full exploitation (development and implementation).

2.4.2. TRLs for plastic pollution

The application of TRL to fields that are not strictly technological is a challenge. EUROqCHARM provides a possible solution to **include TRL into plastic pollution** and other litter to sustain an innovative and mature discussion about monitoring methods (Figure 4).

TRLs are assessed focussing on the single steps of the analytical pipeline used when addressing plastic pollution (sRAP). No experimental or modelling data is available in the literature about TRL applied to the monitoring steps of environmental plastics, so the assessment presented here and will concentrate on methods and technologies that **are most recurrent in the scientific literature after results based on the EUROqCHARM project Systematic Review**. The TRL of sRAP is evaluated by expert opinion according to the criteria in Figure 4.

Figure 4 – Technological Readiness Levels (TRL) used to assess plastic pollution monitoring and research. The nine TRLs are as follows: TRL 1-3 represent fundamental R&D (basic research), TRLs 4-6 scale-up and integration (applied research), and TRLs 7-9 demonstration and full exploitation (development and implementation). Figures adapted from European Space Agency Technological Readiness Levels Scale (<https://www.esa.int>).

For further information on our approach refer to: Aliani, S., Lusher, A.L., Galgani, F., et al., (2023). Reproducibility and Readiness Levels in Plastic Monitoring. *Nature Reviews Earth and Environment* 4, 290-291. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43017-023-00405-0>.

3. Methods

3.1. Description of EUROqCHARM Systematic Review workflow

A Systematic Review (SR) was performed using the open access software, Rayyan (<https://www.rayyan.ai/>), to facilitate the citation screening process. Microsoft Excel was used to compile the extracted information from each paper. Keywords lists were created for each matrix/task group and merged into a single search string. A second list of inclusion and exclusion criteria was created to target methods papers and avoid the inclusion of non-methodological papers. A literature search was performed using Web of Science and Scopus.

The titles and keywords of all papers were checked to reduce non-relevant papers accidentally included in the list. 861 papers were found not relevant for our purposes after this first QA/QC and excluded from further steps. The remaining papers (2429 in total) were included in the title and abstract reading step. Figure 5 reports the workflow of the main steps of the literature search.

Figure 5 – Workflow of the steps of the main literature search.

Next, titles and abstracts of all of the papers were read in pairs. Readers were asked to check whether papers fulfilled the inclusion criteria or if they should be excluded. The pair readers also tagged papers according to environmental matrix. The readers first worked independently (using the blind function in Rayyan), then paired readers achieved consensus for each paper and other non-relevant papers were removed from the citation list. Figure 6 reports the number of papers per compartment.

Figure 6 – Number of papers allocated per compartment.

Teams of readers to read the full papers on the environmental matrices where they held considerable expertise. They were not aware of the work of the other readers, and special care was devoted to foster a blind compilation of papers. Each reader was responsible for **extracting the**

relevant information needed to define RAPs from the peer-reviewed literature. A master excel file was created so that all readers extract the same information across task groups. A series of dropdown menus were created in the Excel file to standardise the extraction of information at each step. Every reader compiled their own version of the Excel file. All files were merged into a single worksheet by single compartments. After which, a global file was created merging data from all compartments. Data in the compartment datasheets were checked for consistency through a quality check (QC). As a result, a large database of information retrieved from peer reviewed literature is now available and available through EUROqCHARM.

3.2. Identification of RAPs

For every compartment and matrix, the extracted data in Excel were analysed to find RAPs. For every analytical step, the most commonly used or relevant methods have been highlighted and if they were replicable and robust enough were considered part of the complete RAP. A theoretical example is reported in Figure 7.

Figure 7 – Theoretical examples of Reproducible Analytical Pathways (RAPs) in assessments of plastics in the environment.

3.3. Technological Readiness Levels of RAPs

Once a Reproducible Analytical Pipeline (RAP) had been identified the next step was to assess its applicability in monitoring programmes. Therefore, it was necessary to assess the **Technological Readiness Level (TRL) of the identified RAPs**.

As described earlier, a detailed RAP analysis was **performed for each step of the analytical procedure**. If the number of entries was $n > 10$ and method have been validated at the laboratory level and in relevant environment (indicated also by sufficient publications from different research groups and geographic diverse area) a TRL of 4 or 5 was considered. When the number of relevant papers was > 20 a TRL of 6 or higher could be assigned as the applied research has moved into the development phase or inclusion in monitoring programmes. The most mature technologies are envisaged to be included in a monitoring protocol, even if they may not necessarily be the most advanced in term of innovation and efficiency.

4. Results

4.1. Plastics in Solids

Much of the literature assessed in the SR focused on macro litter on beaches and shorelines (88% of entries), this likely reflects the advances in methodology and the early adoption into monitoring guidelines. Publications on microplastics dominated the sediment and seafloor category (178 entries). Three major pathways for sampling and analyses of plastic from the different subcompartments were identified as they generally varied with the targeted size fraction of the plastic particles and litter items, i.e. between microplastic, mesoplastic and macrolitter. All data were collected by the task leader and a general quality control/quality assurance performed. Details about results can be found in the corresponding report (Strand et al. 2023).

4.2. Plastics in Water

The number of publications for micro- and mesoplastics started to increase from 2013, while the investigation of nanoplastics started at around 2017. In all cases the highest numbers of publications were reached in 2020. All data were collected by the task leader and a general quality control/quality assurance performed.

RAPs could be extracted for macroplastic analysis, and common pathways could be extracted for visual surveys and net sampling, these were assigned a TRL of 6, although a consensus for monitoring was lacking. Details about results can be found in the corresponding report (Pimpke et al. 2023).

4.3. Plastics in Biota

The number of publications from environmental studies on plastics in biota has strongly increased over the last decade. Whereas only 12 publications were retained by our SR for the period until 2010, up to 37 and 309 publications were retained for the period 2011-2015 and 2016-2020, respectively. All data were collected by the task leader and a general quality control/quality assurance performed.

Sufficient publications to construct RAPs were retrieved for the sub-compartments fish, bivalves, birds and non-bivalve invertebrates. RAPs for plastic determination in birds reach the highest TRL. Determination of nanoplastics in biota is currently still at the stage of basic research, with TRL below 3. Details about results can be found in the corresponding report (De Witte et al. 2023).

4.4. Plastics in Air

The difference between this Task (T1.4) and other tasks of WP 1 is that a much smaller number of papers are available for review and they were insufficient for a full SR. Therefore, the papers on microplastics in air were necessarily analysed using a traditional review approach. The aim remained to identify repeatable patterns in sampling and analysis, which could be indications of future potential RAPs.

Seventy-seven papers related to plastic in the air were identified through the literature review process, only 31 of which included descriptions of analytical methods. It was not possible to identify RAPs, although potential prototypes were highlighted. There was no indication of potential RAPs for nanoparticles. Details about results can be found in the corresponding report (Nikiforov et al. 2023).

5. Discussion

The Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD; Hanke et al. 2013) recommends that an assessment of the suitability of different, existing monitoring methods. The identification of relevant criteria for the inclusion of a method or approach is not an easy task. There is a lot of debate about the criteria, and MSFD identified the following essential elements. Some are summarised below:

- the spatial distribution of survey sites
- the frequency of sampling
- the QA/QC needs
- the arrangements for management/handling of the monitoring metadata at local, national (and/or regional level).

A quantitative description of the frequency of use of analytical procedures, geographic distribution, study areas, tools and metrics has been collected through the EUROqCHARM SR and all systematically extracted method data and metadata provide a synthetic view of existing methods and procedures. It could be concluded that there is a low degree of harmonisation in the use of methods applied to a compartment and amongst compartments (and subcompartments). Furthermore, the scenario is complicated by methodologies which are differently distributed according to geographic area and over time.

Timeseries are the only way to assess if mitigation actions are actually working or not. To build a time series it is important that data from different steps in the series are comparable, but it is also necessary that samplings are regularly even in time. Our SR did not find papers that presented data from a time series built upon regular and repeatable monitoring activity. A lot of effort is still required to achieve a timeseries or a baseline data that can be used to assess the effectiveness of policies. Harmonisation of methods and procedures is a necessary step.

EUROqCHARM recognises that harmonisation for large scale monitoring requires flexibility, comparability and reliability. We identified Reproducible Analytical Pipelines (RAP), resulting in a catalogue of RAP procedures for nano-, micro- and macro-plastics for the four target matrices. Each RAP was validated in terms of Technology Readiness Level (TRL) to decide if further validation is needed.

5.1. Suitability of the EUROqCHARM SR approach

A Systematic Review (SR) is a method to analyse data in literature and is expected to be replicable and objective. Rayyan was applied as a useful Open Access online collaborative tool to provide fundamental support to SR.

Of course, a SR is not perfect, but it has the great advantage that it can be replicated, and many papers can be explored simultaneously. In some cases, the knowledge of literature by top experts was ahead of databases and they can be aware of papers before they are included in Scopus or WoS databases.

Few of the relevant papers were excluded from our SR because authors did not provide relevant information in the title, keyword or abstract. This exemplifies the necessity that authors should put more attention to carefully crafting titles and abstracts, as well as keywords selections. These elements are fundamental for a SR and papers may have been missed or lost during the SR process, if the aim and methodological approach of the work were not clearly presented in the abstract.

5.2. Synthesis of existing methods and procedures

The number of publications on the topic of plastics in the environment has dramatically increased in recent years (Cowger et al. 2020) and our SR shows that the majority of papers have been published after 2015, which reflects the growth in research interest and political relevance on plastics in the environment on a global scale. Our SR also reminds us that studies on environmental plastic have a long history, with earliest studies retrieved going back to 1980.

There was a problem of terminology across different disciplines and geographic areas. The most evident is the use of the word “litter” or “debris” to indicate the waste items found in the environment with a geographic preference for the use of “debris” in North America compared to EU where “litter” is widely used for beach pollution, but less so for water pollution. It is not in the aims of this report to evaluate and modify terminology, but we highlight the different uses observed through the SR and encourage harmonisation at terminological level.

In the initial stage of scientific publishing on the issue of environmental plastic, papers focused on reporting what was found in different environments and method descriptions were often incomplete. In the most recent literature, quasi-standard protocols were more often used. This observation was also reported in a critical assessment on methodological developments in microplastics research (Rist et al. 2021).

Grey literature. There is a lot of grey literature on environmental plastics available on the internet or in repositories of organisations and companies. In some instances, reports do not have the minimal requirements to be considered in our SR. For example, they were a simple collection of items and did not report aims and methods. In other cases, there was a strong bias toward an opinion, which limited their level in terms of scientific contribution. Therefore, a lot of grey literature was excluded from our analysis. The grey literature we explored was from thematic working groups and official reports of national entities or scientific projects. These reports mainly described expert identified protocols and suggested their use, sometimes with detailed lists of procedures or steps.

In general, reports did not assess the performance of their guidelines. For example, they did not report information on the geographical distribution of methods nor an assessment of use and usability at local and global scale. They also did not consider technological readiness as a tool to support the development of new methods for the years to come. This information can be extracted from our SR dataset, which provides a valuable asset to evaluate the guidelines’ incorporation in the community. Lastly, by limiting the grey literature search to English language it is likely that many national level monitoring guidelines and publications were overlooked.

5.3. Reproducible Analytical Pipelines (RAP) for monitoring

The concept of Reproducible Analytical Pipeline (RAP) is used in environmental plastic monitoring for the first time, although it is already widely used in other fields. The fundamental steps in the analytical process have been identified and methodologies that have been used regularly and are reported in literature are incorporated in the suggested analytical pipelines.

The purpose of our RAP analysis was not to assess if the identified pipeline is useful or adequate as a monitoring protocol but aims to report methods most described in literature. This excludes new and promising methods, which may deserve attention in the future, but are not yet compliant to the MSFD requirements for monitoring. A critical revision of the relevant characteristics of RAPs was carried out by Technological Readiness.

Survey Design. There are aspects of survey design that were not considered in the SR, such as whether site selection was probabilistic or whether dimensions (beach length/area, haul

duration/speed, etc.) were standardised or variable. Other elements not included were spatial scale and structure of sampling and independence of data points/autocorrelation, temporal scale of sampling, level of replication etc. The number of possibilities in designing the survey is too wide and variable to consider them all. The main aspects considered focused on the sampling area, the Regional Sea Convention, whether there was repeated sampling (monitoring) or single points in time (research) and whether studies used a standardised protocol (e.g., OSPAR) or a method of their own design. The relevant information has been extracted and analysed for every compartment.

Sample collection. Harmonisation of methods also includes harmonisation of sampling tools. Many sampling gears and procedures are used or have been used over time and a reduction could be welcome. Within this work, we report if a certain tool is having an acceptable TRL. However, the definition of a standard shall be based upon dedicated experiments and not only on wide use.

Sample preparation. There are many steps in sample preparation (visual and density separation, filtration, digestion) that have been identified and many are commonly applied to different compartments and plastic sizes. However, there are differences in application and frequency of use, so sample preparation techniques have been considered separately for every situation and cannot be generalised into a single description of characteristics.

Analytical detection. After plastics have been separated from the environmental matrix, the analytical procedure mainly depends on the size of the sample and the size of the plastics, and many elements are in common among the different compartments. Some analytical technologies (e.g. FTIR and Raman) are widely used and mature. They provide polymer identification for smaller particles over a reasonable time, especially when connected to image analysis. Identification of large items depends mainly on visual identified particles.

QA/QC. Control of environmental contamination and the use of procedural blank is often missing in older papers, which makes the comparison of old and new data critical for smaller particles. Information about QA/QC for larger items is usually not reported and dedicated experiments are required to control the quality of data about macroscopic particles. It is noteworthy that the contamination is probably minimal and QA/QC shall probably focus on data acquisition and management for larger plastics.

Data Management. The SR provided an overview on how scientists managed their data on environmental plastics, based on peer-reviewed scientific literature. Although there are many repositories where data can be stored, in many cases original data are not reported or they are just referred to in the appendix of papers. Many additional information can be extracted from our SR database, including some general information on the state of this science. For example, we found that the scientific community has improved a lot with time since the first papers, but in many cases original data are not reported even today. This is an obstacle for the definition of baselines and makes the build-up of timeseries difficult. For this reason, we follow and encourage the FAIR principles behind Open Access data.

5.4. Technological Readiness for critical revisions of monitoring methods.

The Technological Readiness Level (TRL) is applied for the first time to the science of environmental plastics thus following the general EU Directive that recommends its application in many fields. TRL provided a useful synthesis of the status and maturity of a certain technique. As any new application, it is open to improvements, but here its use to synthesise a wide range of information is appreciated. More research is definitely needed on the use of TRL to fully exploit it to assess and decide about monitoring protocols.

Parallel to protocols that have high TRL and are already included in running protocols (e.g., filtration techniques or beach monitoring), other monitoring steps have a TRL under the threshold required to be included in monitoring programs. Only mature methods that have been considered relevant to other WPs were implemented in WP1. Details about TRL can be found in relevant matrix reports.

6. Conclusion

Existing monitoring methods dedicated to the quantification of nano-, micro-, and macro-plastics in different compartments (water, soil/sediment, air, biota) have been identified, based on a systematic literature review (SR). A large set of 3290 papers have been published in scientific peer review literature that were matching one or more of the selected keywords of our SR. We removed reviews and obviously non relevant papers through a process of title screening and pairwise title and abstract reading. Finally full literature reading and data extraction focused on 1859 papers.

A large data set of information about methodologies is made available to support WP2 and WP3. The most promising methods were suggested for validation and quality control in WP2 or direct implementation into WP3. The data set will soon be made public in Excel format in the EUROqCHARM web repository (Zenodo).

The major conclusions deduced from the SR process and following analysis were:

1. Many publications focused on the OSPAR region and the Mediterranean. Within Europe, research studies on plastics are not equally distributed. e.g., for the matrix biota, no publications were identified in the Black Sea.
2. An impressive number of papers addressed methodological aspects but in many instances the description of methods provided by authors was insufficient to understand and reconstruct the methodology used. Therefore, an acceptable scientific level is not reached when relevant information about methods, sampling positions and reagents were missing. This is a big problem for scientific quality, to replicate the experiments, and to compare data among different papers.
3. Much of the recent literature does not follow the latest methodological recommendations. People tend to apply methods already applied in other research campaigns, and only in few instances did they push method development. Similarly, studies which applied routine monitoring approaches tended to use older techniques with little technological improvement. Applying updated methods to already running sampling campaigns could be sometimes regarded as impossible as doing so would mess up long-term data. If reference to the difference between the improved methods is not provided, people will continue using the old methods to have comparable data.
4. Differences can be identified between continents in the targeted compartments and sub-compartments as well as in the methods applied.
5. Only a small part of the publications identified through the SR make their full dataset publicly available within the supportive information or within Open Access data repositories.
6. There are size barriers in analysis and no universal method is applicable for all sizes. Different sizes lead to different monitoring methods and different suggestions for standard approaches.
7. The QA/QC is weakly described in many papers. Whereas this could be expected for older literature (>5 years), more recent publications should meet minimum requirements.

8. Too many papers are lacking detailed information on contamination and no information is provided to assess if background contamination originates from the environment or just fieldwork, procedural or lab contamination.
9. Many papers do not report the lower size limit of particles that can be detected by the method.
10. Publications can report mean abundances while other publications calculate the median.

RECOMMENDATIONS:

1. It is necessary to agree upon a common “state of the art recommendation of methodologies” and share it as much as possible. It is not advisable to work on method development in a monitoring programme without addressing a way to compare new data with traditional methods.
2. The RAPs developed by EUROqCHARM should form a basis for large scale harmonisation (for monitoring studies).
3. Environmental authorities and regulators should support harmonisation of plastic analysis methods within all European regions, both marine as well as terrestrial.
4. Authors and referees of papers should pay attention to method description. Editor and referees are encouraged to ask for proper methodology descriptions.
5. It is necessary to study how data from different continents can be harmonised or compared.
6. It is important to share FAIR data in repositories or as supplements to papers.
7. Avoid using a method that is not suitable for the target size class of plastics. For instance, macroplastic and other litter found into manta nets shall be considered accidental and cannot be compared to data from sightings.
8. Use comparable methods for all compartments, especially solids as much as possible or provide a way to reference the method used to standard RAPs.
9. Monitoring studies on plastics in biota should select species based on the targeted particle size as well as other characteristics such as geographical distribution, ecological niche and conservation status.
10. Methods for nanoplastic determination in the marine or terrestrial environment are not developed enough to include in monitoring.
11. More research is needed on air sampling procedures to exploit PM10 monitoring network.
12. A set of minimum requirements for QA/QC should be developed, and the use of all QA/QC measures should be reported in papers and published datasets.
13. For each method, the lower size limit should be reported. It can depend on the shape of the particle (fibre versus particle).

14. Monitoring guidelines should also provide data handling information, including the reporting of processed data (e.g. reporting of mean or median, using arithmetic or logarithmic mean). Including details in methods description, for instance on how to calculate the mean (e.g. with or without log transformation).
15. Harmonisation (or monitoring) efforts should include the handling of background or laboratory contamination.

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